

Integrating Societal Development into Flood Damage Models

Toke Emil Panduro and Tenaw G. Abate

Abstract

This workingpaper examines three methodological approaches for incorporating socio-economic and land-use dynamics into future flood-damage calculations: (1) sorting models that describe spatial equilibrium outcomes arising from household and firm location choices, (2) agent-based models that simulate adaptive behavior and interaction among heterogeneous agents, and (3) predictive models that use empirical and machine-learning techniques to project land-use and socio-economic change. We undertake a theoretical synthesis to evaluate the conceptual foundations, data requirements, and modelling implications of each approach. The motivation for this work lies in the limitations of current Danish flood damage models, which largely treat exposure and vulnerability as static, even though ongoing urbanization, demographic shifts, and behavioral adaptation are reshaping spatial patterns of risk. Without explicit representations of societal development, future flood-risk estimates may mischaracterize both the scale and distribution of expected damages. The paper's contribution is twofold. First, it evaluates the methodological trade-offs across predictive, equilibrium-based, and agent-based approaches, highlighting where each paradigm is limited and where it offers unique leverage for representing socio-economic change. Second, by providing a coherent economic–spatial–hazard framework, the paper establishes the conceptual foundations for incorporating dynamic exposure into future risk calculations. Looking ahead, the analysis sets an agenda for developing land-use change modelling frameworks that can support long-term climate-resilience planning and strengthen the alignment between spatial development and adaptation policy.

Keywords: Flood damage models; societal development; dynamic exposure; land-use change; flood risk assessment; climate adaptation; spatial modelling; sorting models; spatial-temporal agent-based models; spatial predictive models

Administrative Information

Working Paper Series

Series title: Aarhus University – Environmental Social Science and Geography Working Paper Series
Institution: Aarhus University, Department of Environmental Science
Section: Environmental Social Science and Geography
Working Paper Number: ESGO-WP-2026-02
Version: 1.0
Year: 2026

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Funding

This research was funded by the Danish Environmental Agency from the Research Reserve 2025 as part of the project: Udvikling af ensartede metodiske retningslinjer for opgørelse af skadesværdier.

Working Paper Status and Disclaimer

This paper is part of the *Aarhus University – Environmental Social Science and Geography Working Paper Series*. Working papers are preliminary research outputs circulated to stimulate discussion and invite comments. The views expressed are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the funding body or the affiliated institutions.

Availability and DOI

This working paper is publicly available via Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18233328>

Citation Suggestion

Panduro, T. E. & Abate, T. G. (2026). Integrating Societal Development into Flood Damage Models, Aarhus University, Department of Environmental Science, Environmental Social Science and Geography Working Paper Series, Version 1.0. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18233328>

Acknowledgement

This working paper was prepared by Toke Emil Panduro and Tenaw Gedefaw Abate (Department of Environmental Science, Aarhus University) as part of the project: “*Udvikling af ensartede metodiske retningslinjer for opgørelse af skadesværdier*”. Valuable discussions and inputs were provided by other participants in the work package, including Karsten Arnbjerg-Nielsen, Cecilie Thrysoe, and Raphael Payet-Burin (DMI), as well as Per Skougaard Kaspersen, Kirsten Halsnæs, Martin Drews, and Kaija Jumppanen Andersen (DTU Management).

1. Introduction

Understanding and modeling the impact of societal land-use development on flood damages is increasingly recognized as a key challenge in climate risk assessment and adaptation planning (Hallegatte et al., 2020; Jongman et al., 2014). While advances in hydrological and hydraulic modeling have greatly improved the representation of physical processes, the human and socio-economic dimensions of risk - population distribution, land use dynamics, income growth, and behavioral adaptation - remain only partially integrated into existing damage models (Bouwer, 2011; Aerts et al., 2018). This limitation affects not only global applications but also national-scale assessments in Denmark, where urban densification, demographic transitions, and land-use regulations interact with local flood exposures (Nielsen et al., 2023). Moreover, recent Danish evidence shows that these interactions often reinforce rather than mitigate societal vulnerability: continued residential and commercial investments in exposed coastal and low-lying areas increase the concentration of assets at risk, and institutional incentives - such as municipal dependence on property tax revenue - can encourage development in areas that would ideally be left to flood (DØRS, 2021). As a result, Denmark, like many other countries, is likely on a trajectory where socio-economic development is still amplifying rather than reducing future flood damages.

Flood damage models typically estimate expected losses as a function of hazard (characteristics of the flooding event itself - for example, flood depth, extent, duration, and probability of occurrence), exposure (the quantity and value of people, buildings, infrastructure, and economic activities located in areas that might be flooded), and vulnerability (the fragility of buildings, preparedness measures, elevation, drainage capacity, or household resilience) (Goyal & Mukherjee, 2025). Yet, exposure and vulnerability are themselves dynamic, endogenously shaped by societal development and land-use changes, i.e., through urbanization, infrastructure investment, zoning regulations, and household or firm location decisions (Winsemius et al., 2016).

In Denmark, patterns of coastal construction and urban expansion have shaped where people and assets are located relative to pluvial and coastal flood hazards (Kaspersen et al., 2017). These trends influence both exposure and vulnerability, as some municipalities experience growing concentrations of high-value assets, while others undergo limited development and asset growth (Chen et al., 2020; Kuchler & Wessel, 2021; Samuelsson et al., 2021). New housing developments in coastal zones such as Køge Bay and Aalborg's waterfront illustrate how economic development and housing demand continue to coincide with elevated flood risk (Arnbjerg-Nielsen et al., 2015). To our knowledge, no Danish flood loss analysis incorporates dynamic socio-economic exposure; existing assessments rely on present-day land use and demographic data. This static approach risks underestimating or overestimating long-term losses. The challenge, therefore, is to develop a quantitative linkage between future societal development and flood damage modeling.

At the micro-level, urban economics and spatial equilibrium theory provide a tractable starting point by modeling location choice as a utility-maximizing process (Rosen, 1974; Roback, 1982). These sorting models can describe how households and firms allocate themselves spatially based on amenities, wages, rents, or risk exposure (Kuminoff et al., 2013). However, their equilibrium assumptions and static nature make them less suitable for analyzing transitional dynamics or behavioral adaptation to emerging risks.

Agent-Based Models offer an alternative by simulating decentralized decision-making and interactions among heterogeneous agents (Farmer & Foley, 2009; Filatova et al., 2009). Such models have been successfully applied to represent adaptive urban growth, migration under risk perception, and the co-evolution of infrastructure and exposure (Haer et al., 2017).

Finally, data-driven predictive models, leveraging machine learning and spatial statistics, provide powerful empirical tools to forecast socio-economic and land-use changes (Reis et al., 2015; Schröder et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2022). Löwe et al. (2019) demonstrate, using Danish urban data, how lot-scale development parameters can be derived empirically to simulate future urban growth and densification patterns. This study underscores the suitability of predictive approaches in a Danish context, especially given the wealth of detailed spatial and cadastral datasets, e.g., GeoDanmark spatial database (GeoDanmark, 2025), BBR building register

(Vurderingsstyrelsen, 2025), DAR address register (Klimadatastyrelsen, 2025) - that allow granular predictions of population distribution, built-up area expansion, and land-use change.

Each of these paradigms - equilibrium-based, non-equilibrium behavioral, and empirical predictive - offers advantages and disadvantages for integrating societal development into flood damage models. The objective of this report is to examine how future societal development can be incorporated quantitatively into flood damage models, both in the short and long term, and to evaluate which methodological approaches are most suitable in a Danish context. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Develop a theoretical framework linking household and firm location decisions to spatial exposure and vulnerability patterns.
2. Evaluate three complementary modeling paradigms—sorting models, agent-based models, and predictive models—for their ability to represent socio-economic dynamics.
3. Assess their feasibility, data requirements, and integration potential with existing Danish flood damage models and national climate adaptation frameworks.

A literature review will map existing international and Danish methods for linking socio-economic development to flood risk, while the theoretical synthesis will provide conceptual foundations for model integration. The output will be a set of recommendations on how to include societal development in future Danish flood damage calculations.

This work contributes to the Danish flood risk modeling agenda by identifying a key limitation in existing approaches—namely, the absence of dynamic socio-economic representation—and by outlining a structured pathway for addressing this gap. Conceptually, we clarify how individual and collective location choices shape future exposure and vulnerability. Methodologically, we synthesize the main modeling approaches that can incorporate these dynamics and assess their relevance for damage assessments. The findings are expected to support:

- More realistic projections of future flood damages under alternative socio-economic scenarios,
- Better integration of spatial planning and economic analysis in adaptation policy, and
- The design of scalable modeling frameworks that can inform both national policy and local planning tools.

In this way, this paper provides a critical bridge between physical risk modeling and societal change analysis, contributing both to the scientific foundation and to the policy relevance of Danish flood risk assessment.

2. Theoretical Framework: Location Choice and Risk

This section outlines a conceptual and analytical framework for integrating societal development into damage modeling. The goal is to capture how individuals and firms make location decisions, how these decisions aggregate into spatial patterns of exposure, and how different modeling paradigms (equilibrium, non-equilibrium, and predictive) can represent these dynamics.

2.1. Household Location Choice

We begin from the premise that households make location choices to maximize their utility functions under given constraints.

Let household i choose a location j to maximize its indirect utility:

$$U_{ij} = u(Y_i - P_j, A_j, R_j, \epsilon_{ij})$$

where: Y_i is income of household i , P_j is housing cost at location j , A_j is amenity and accessibility characteristics (e.g., proximity to schools, jobs, green areas), R_j is perceived risk (e.g., flood exposure, insurance cost), ϵ_{ij} is idiosyncratic preference shock.

Assuming a random utility framework, the probability that individual i chooses location j is given by the multinomial logit form:

$$P_{ij} = \frac{\exp(V_{ij})}{\sum_{k \in J} \exp(V_{ik})} \quad 2$$

where V_{ij} is the deterministic component of U_{ij} .

Households select the location that yields the highest U_{ij} . In equilibrium, housing prices P_j adjust until no household can increase its utility by moving, given income and local characteristics:

$$U_i = \bar{U} \quad \forall i \in J$$

This defines a spatial equilibrium in the spirit of Rosen (1974) and Roback (1982), where prices equalize marginal utilities across space.

Risk enters utility negatively, i.e. $\partial U / \partial R_j < 0$, but its impact depends on perception and capacity:

1. Risk perception bias – households may misjudge probabilities or rely on past experience (Gigerenzer & Gaissmaier, 2011).
2. Adaptive capacity – insurance, elevated housing, or community protection can reduce *effective* exposure (Haer et al., 2019).
3. Income heterogeneity – wealthier households may tolerate higher risks for superior amenities (e.g. waterfronts).

Hence, equilibrium exposure is not purely a function of physical risk but also of behavioral, informational, and institutional factors. Agent-based models are well suited for capturing these heterogeneities, allowing for gradual adaptation and imperfect learning rather than instantaneous equilibrium adjustment.

2.2. Firm Location Choice

Firm n selects location j to maximize expected profit:

$$\Pi_{nj} = f(L_{nj}, K_{nj}, A_j) - C_{nj} - D(R_j) \quad 3$$

where: L_{nj}, K_{nj} are labor and capital inputs at location j , A_j represents location-specific attributes or amenities that affect firm productivity (such as infrastructure quality, agglomeration effects, local institutional and regulatory environment and environmental quality); $f(\cdot)$ represents production function capturing local productivity and market access, C_j is local cost components (wages, transport, land, regulation), and $D(R_j)$ is expected risk-related costs (damage, insurance, business interruption)

As in the household case, firms face a trade-off between accessibility and exposure. Denser, coastal, or low-lying urban areas (e.g. Copenhagen, Odense, or Esbjerg) offer high productivity but also greater flood risk. Over time, technological change and spatial planning policies shift the profitability of these locations, influencing how economic activity clusters or disperses in risk zones.

The combination of household and firm choices determines the spatial distribution of population, employment, and capital—core determinants of flood exposure in *skadesmodeller*.

2.3. Equilibrium (Sorting Model) View

Under equilibrium, locations satisfy $U_i = \bar{U}$ and $\Pi_n = \bar{\Pi}$ for all active households and firms. This condition implies that both households and firms are spatially indifferent across locations where they are present. For households, equal utility across locations means that wages, housing costs, and local amenities adjust such that no individual can improve their welfare by migrating to another area. Similarly, for firms, equal profits across operating locations indicate that factor prices and productivity conditions adjust so that no firm has an incentive to relocate or enter another region. Inactive locations—those with no residents or firms—are characterized by lower utility or profit levels and therefore remain unoccupied in equilibrium.

This equilibrium condition captures the essence of spatial adjustment in urban and regional models. When mobility of labor and capital is allowed, any regional advantage - such as higher productivity or lower costs - triggers flows of people and firms that erode these differences over time. The resulting equilibrium equalizes utility and profit across active locations, ensuring that all observed differences in wages, rents, and firm productivity are fully compensated by other location-specific attributes such as transport costs, amenities, or agglomeration effects. In this way, the conditions $U_i = \bar{U}$ and $\Pi_n = \bar{\Pi}$ define the steady-state spatial distribution of population and economic activity.

When local flood risk R_j increases, both households and firms experience reductions in expected utility and profits. In spatial equilibrium, these changes trigger compensating adjustments in wages w_j and housing prices P_j until utility and profitability are equalized across locations. For households, higher risk reduces location attractiveness, leading some to migrate away. This outmigration lowers local housing demand and may also tighten labor supply. The net effect on wages depends on which side of the market adjusts faster: if labor supply contracts more than firm demand, wages rise to compensate workers for higher risk; if firms exit or downscale production faster than households leave, labor demand falls and wages may instead decline.

For firms, increased risk - through higher expected damage, insurance costs, or business interruption - reduces expected profits. In response, firms may relocate, reduce capital investment, or negotiate lower land rents. Consequently, the equilibrium condition $U_i = \bar{U}$ and $\Pi_n = \bar{\Pi}$ is restored through a new combination of wages, rents, and local population. In most cases, the dominant adjustment channel is a reduction in land and housing prices, which capitalizes the risk into property values, while wage responses depend on labor and capital mobility. Together, these mechanisms ensure that despite local shocks in risk exposure, the spatial equilibrium is maintained through market-mediated redistributions of risk premiums across space.

2.4. Dynamic (Agent-based) View

In reality, we contend that adjustments are gradual and path-dependent, and that equilibrium is more a construct of theoretical abstraction than an empirical regularity. For a comprehensive critique of equilibrium modeling in economics, see, for example, Stiglitz (2018) and Guzman & Stiglitz (2020). In contrast to classical economic models Agent-based models capture how households and firms learn, migrate, and adapt based on experience and social interaction, alleviated from the assumption of equilibrium:

$$\Pr(\text{move}_{i,j \rightarrow k,t}) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-\lambda \Delta U_{i,j \rightarrow k,t})} \quad 4$$

This is a logit-type choice probability that gives the probability that household i moves from location j to location k at time t , based on the expected *utility gain* from that move, $\Delta U_{i,j \rightarrow k,t}$. The parameter $\lambda > 0$ captures decision sensitivity - higher λ means more deterministic behavior (agents are more likely to move if the gain is positive).

The expected gain from relocation is given by:

$$\Delta U_{i,j \rightarrow k,t} = U_{ik,t} - U_{ij,t} - M_{i,jk,t} + \beta(E_t[U_{ik,t+1}] - E_t[U_{ij,t+1}]) \quad 5$$

where $M_{i,jk,t}$ is migration or moving cost (financial, social, or psychological) from j to k at time t ; β is a Discount factor, $0 < \beta < 1$, weighting expected future utilities and $E_t[\cdot]$ is the expectation formed at time t about future utilities.

This formulation captures dynamic location adjustment under uncertainty and mobility frictions. The probability that an agent relocates depends on the *expected net utility gain* from moving, combining both current advantages (e.g., lower risk or better amenities) and anticipated future benefits, discounted by β . The logistic structure implies that moves are probabilistic rather than deterministic—agents may remain in suboptimal locations due to imperfect information, habit, or high moving costs $M_{i,jk,t}$. Over time, as risks, amenities, and expectations evolve, this framework allows for path-dependent spatial dynamics, where adaptation to changing flood risk or economic opportunity unfolds gradually rather than instantaneously.

2.5. Predictive data-driven models

Predictive models rely on empirical relationships between observed variables to estimate or forecast spatial patterns, without explicitly modeling behavioral optimization or equilibrium conditions. In their most general form, predictive models can be represented as:

$$\hat{Y}_j = g(X_j) \tag{6}$$

where \hat{Y}_j is the predicted outcome in location j - such as population density, land use, or expected damage - and X_j is a vector of explanatory variables that may include income levels, flood risk indicators, accessibility, infrastructure, and environmental attributes.

The function $g(\cdot)$ can take many forms, ranging from classical statistical approaches to machine-learning algorithms such as random forests, gradient boosting, and neural networks (Merz et al., 2020). These data-driven approaches can capture complex, non-linear interactions and high-dimensional relationships that are difficult to specify within traditional economic frameworks (Mosavi et al., 2018)

2.6. Comparison of the three modeling approaches

The three modeling paradigms—sorting models, agent-based models, and predictive models—offer competing strengths and limitations for representing how societal development shapes future flood exposure and damages (see table 1). Their relevance varies with the type of decision problem, the time horizon of interest, and the institutional setting in which flood risk assessments are conducted.

Sorting models provide a theoretically grounded framework for analyzing long-run spatial equilibria. Because they derive location outcomes from utility- and profit-maximizing behavior, they allow welfare-consistent counterfactuals and integrate naturally with economic valuation methods (Kuminoff et al., 2013). These features make sorting models well-suited for evaluating policy scenarios such as zoning changes, infrastructure investments, or flood protection strategies. Sorting models are constrained by strong assumptions of market equilibrium and perfect information among households and firms—assumptions that recent work argues are theoretical abstractions rather than empirically observable conditions. Even minor informational frictions can induce a continuum of disequilibrium outcomes (Stiglitz, 2018; Guzman & Stiglitz, 2020).

Agent-based models take a fundamentally different approach by simulating dynamic interactions among heterogeneous, boundedly rational agents. Agent-based models are able to represent adaptation processes, path dependence, social learning, and localized responses to changing risk conditions (Farmer & Foley, 2009; Haer et al., 2017). This makes them particularly valuable for exploring how households, firms, and municipalities might adjust to flood hazards over time, and how these micro-level decisions aggregate into emergent spatial patterns. Their flexibility comes with challenges: Agent-based models require detailed behavioral data and careful calibration, and their departure from neoclassical assumptions can limit their ability to deliver welfare metrics comparable to equilibrium models.

Predictive models, including both statistical and machine-learning approaches, emphasize empirical accuracy and scalability. They integrate diverse datasets and can capture complex, nonlinear relationships without extensive theoretical specification. In the short term, predictive models often perform well because the underlying drivers of land-use patterns and demographic change tend to remain relatively stable (Schröder et al., 2022; Löwe et al., 2019). Over longer horizons, however, their performance deteriorates because they do not represent the behavioural or economic mechanisms that generate land-use change (Wang et al., 2022; Merz et al., 2020). As a result, purely data-driven projections are prone to becoming obsolete when fundamentals evolve, such as through shifts in planning policy or demographic transitions (Löwe et al., 2020).

Although the three approaches can each inform flood risk assessment, they should be viewed as competing modeling strategies that embody fundamentally different assumptions about behavior, dynamics, and predictability. Predictive models are often superior for short-term forecasting because they extrapolate recent patterns, but they lack the structural mechanisms needed to remain valid when underlying socio-economic fundamentals change. In contrast, sorting models and Agent-based models are potentially more robust to long-term shifts, as both embed explicit representations of behavior and adaptation—whether through equilibrium conditions in sorting models or through bounded rationality and interaction in Agent-based models. In this sense, the relaxation of strict theoretical assumptions in Agent-based models is an analytical strength, enabling them to capture behavioral dynamics that equilibrium models abstract from. These distinctions highlight that the choice of modeling approach depends on the time horizon and the nature of the socio-economic processes one seeks to represent.

Table 1. Comparison of Modeling Approaches for Integrating Societal Development in Damage Models

Modeling Approach	Strengths	Limitations	Danish Relevance^a
Sorting Models (Equilibrium-based)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Theoretical foundation (utility/profit maximization)▪ Enables welfare-consistent counterfactuals (e.g., zoning, flood protection)▪ Integrates naturally with economic valuation frameworks	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Assumes equilibrium and perfect information▪ High computational and data requirements for calibration	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Suitable for national- and municipal-level policy evaluation (e.g., land-use planning, housing markets)▪ Can be linked to register data and property value statistics
Agent-Based Models (ABM) (Dynamic behavioral simulation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Captures adaptation, path dependence, and local interactions▪ Represents heterogeneous agents and bounded rationality▪ Can simulate emergent effects of policies and infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ High data and calibration demands▪ Breaks with neoclassical Economics	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Useful for assessing long-term adaptation strategies in flood-prone municipalities (e.g., Vejle, Odense)
Predictive Models (Empirical or ML-based)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ High predictive accuracy and scalability▪ Flexible integration of large and diverse datasets▪ Low theoretical specification burden	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Limited interpretability and welfare insight▪ Sensitive to structural changes (policy, behavior)▪ Risk of overfitting and reduced transparency	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Effective for national short-term damage estimation systems

^a The "Danish Relevance" column reflects how each modeling paradigm aligns with specific institutions, planning processes, and decision contexts within Denmark's flood risk governance system.

3. Operationalizing Societal Development in Damage Models

3.1. Conceptual Integration

The theoretical model in Section 2 provided a microeconomic foundation for understanding how households and firms make location decisions under risk and amenity trade-offs. These decisions shape the spatial distribution of people, buildings, and economic activity, and hence determine future exposure and vulnerability. Operationalizing societal development in damage modeling therefore requires linking these behavioral and spatial processes to a formal representation of expected flood losses.

In flood risk analysis, expected damage in a given year is not the result of a single hazard value but of an entire probability distribution of flood events, each associated with a different level of severity. Flood severity may range from shallow, high-frequency events to rare but extreme inundations. Climate change is expected to shift this distribution over time, so adverse severe events become more frequent. Let r denote flood severity (e.g., water depth), and let $f_R(r, t)$ represent the time-dependent probability density function of flood severities. The function $f_R(r, t)$ reflects both natural variability and long-term climatic trends that alter the frequency and intensity of extreme events.

For any potential event of severity r , losses depend on two components: exposure and vulnerability. Exposure, $Z(r, t)$, captures the value of assets and population affected by an event of severity r . Because deeper floods reach additional buildings and infrastructure, exposure is an increasing function of severity. Exposure also evolves over time due to demographic change, construction activity, and permanent adaptation measures such as dikes or storm-surge barriers that eliminate losses for certain severity ranges. Vulnerability, $V(r, t)$, captures the fraction of exposed value that is lost when flooding of severity r occurs. Vulnerability is shaped by things like building codes, construction materials, and temporary protective measures such as water tubes or flood gates. Both $Z(r, t)$ and $V(r, t)$ may change substantially over time as societal development, adaptation investments, and regulatory standards evolve.

Let the loss function $S(r, t)$ map exposure and vulnerability into monetary damage:

$$S(r, t) = S(Z(r, t), V(r, t)) \quad 7$$

Given the full distribution of possible events, the expected annual damage at time t is:

$$E[D(t)] = \int_0^{\infty} S(Z(r, t), V(r, t)) f_R(r, t) dr \quad 8$$

This formulation makes explicit that expected damages depend on:

1. The hazard distribution $f_R(r, t)$, which changes with accelerating climate change.
2. Exposure $Z(r, t)$, which is determined by the evolving spatial distribution of people, buildings, and infrastructure.
3. Vulnerability $V(r, t)$, which reflects how sensitive exposed assets are to flooding, conditional on building characteristics and adaptation measures.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework linking societal development to expected flood damages.

Figure 1 shows that expected flood damages at time t are determined by the interaction between the hazard distribution $f_R(r, t)$, exposure $Z(r, t)$, and vulnerability $V(r, t)$. Societal development influences flood risk primarily by shaping the spatial distribution of assets and populations (exposure) and their susceptibility to damage (vulnerability), while hazard probabilities are driven by climatic and hydrological processes.

Societal development influences flood risk primarily through its effects on $Z(r, t)$ and $V(r, t)$. Location choices by households and firms produce spatial patterns of exposure, while regulatory standards, investment decisions, and adaptive behaviour shape vulnerability. A modeling framework that seeks to integrate societal development into flood damage calculations must therefore describe the pathways through which demographic, economic, and planning processes translate into changes in exposure and vulnerability across the full hazard distribution.

3.2. Data Foundations

Danish data infrastructure provides an exceptionally strong basis for modelling how societal development shapes future exposure to flood damages. Because the three modelling paradigms considered in this working paper, i.e., sorting models, agent-based models, and predictive statistical models, differ in their empirical requirements, it is important to assess the extent to which existing datasets can support each of them, especially for predicting future social and land-use dynamics that determine exposure.

A key advantage of the Danish context is the availability of detailed administrative registers covering individuals, households, buildings, and firms. Microdata includes information on income, wealth, education, migration, employment, and family status, accessible through Danmarks Statistik's secure servers. All buildings in Denmark are documented in the BBR register, which provides precise geolocation, size, use, construction materials, and structural characteristics of all buildings among other things (Vurderingsstyrelsen, 2025). These data can be linked to property transactions through the Ejerfortegnelsen – Handelsoplysninger register (Geodatastyrelsen, 2025). Firm-level information at the address level, which includes industry codes and employee counts, can be found in the CVR and PNR registers (Erhvervsstyrelsen, 2024a). Furthermore, accounting data for incorporated firms (A/S, ApS, K/S) are available through the Business Authority (Erhvervsstyrelsen, 2024b).

Geospatial datasets form the second core component of the empirical foundation. Detailed land-use layers from GeoDanmark (GeoDanmark, 2025) and Aarhus University's Basemap (Gregor, 2025) provide high-resolution representations of the built environment, infrastructure, and landscape. These datasets allow sorting models to incorporate spatially explicit risk and amenity attributes, enable agent-based models to represent dynamic interactions across the physical landscape, and serve as central features for training and validating predictive exposure and damage models.

Planning and policy datasets—including municipal plans, zoning regulations, and DK2020 adaptation strategies—provide information on existing and future intended and use, densification priorities, and proposed protection measures. These sources are valuable for constructing policy scenarios, yet they do not represent forecasts of actual development trajectories. The data can be retrieved from the plandata cite (Plan- og Landdistrikstyrelsen, 2025). Planning documents reflect political aspirations and often underestimate uncertainty, particularly regarding behavioral responses and market-driven deviations (Löwe et al., 2020). For modelling purposes, planning data are best treated as scenario inputs for sorting models and agent-based models, or as auxiliary predictors in statistical models.

Historical damage and loss records from insurance companies and Naturskaderådet constitute an important empirical basis for estimating and validating loss functions. These data capture observed consequences of past flood events and can reveal behavioral responses to changing risk conditions. They are particularly important for calibrating empirical vulnerability relationships in predictive models and agent-based models, and for testing the plausibility of exposure patterns implied by sorting models.

Overall, Denmark’s data landscape is well-suited to all three modelling paradigms. The availability of rich microdata and high-resolution geospatial datasets enables detailed modelling of societal development and land-use change—an essential step toward projecting future exposure. The principal remaining limitations concern systematic access to historical loss data and more consistent representation of adaptation measures, both of which would strengthen calibration and scenario evaluation across modelling approaches.

Table 2. Overview of data availability and their use in sorting models, Agent based models and predictive models

Data Type	Sorting Models	Agent-Based Models	Predictive Statistical Models
Register data (population, housing, firms, income, migration, valuations)	Enables estimation of preference heterogeneity, location choices, wages, and productivity; strong empirical foundation for equilibrium modeling.	Provides micro-level heterogeneity for initializing agents and calibrating behavioural rules (mobility, adaptation).	Supplies high-quality covariates for exposure, land-use change, and property-level risk prediction.
Geospatial data (DEMs, land use, infrastructure)	Supports construction of spatially explicit risk components in utility/profit functions.	Allows dynamic updating of hazard conditions in simulations; necessary for spatial interaction processes.	Central input features for statistical and ML-based exposure and damage estimation.
Planning & policy data (municipal plans, zoning, DK2020)	Useful for counterfactual policy scenarios but not as deterministic forecasts.	Can be encoded as rules, constraints, or interventions; well suited for exploring deviations from planned development.	May serve as auxiliary predictors but prone to underestimating uncertainty.
Historical damage data (insurance claims, Naturskaderådet)	Indirectly useful for validating exposure implications.	Supports calibration of vulnerability and adaptation behaviour.	Essential for estimating and validating empirical loss functions.
Building & infrastructure data (BBR, SVUR, construction characteristics)	Key for characterizing housing supply and spatial heterogeneity.	Enables detailed modeling location choices.	Important covariates for building-level damage prediction.

4. Literature on application of model types

This section reviews applied studies that have implemented sorting models, agent-based models, and predictive models to evaluate flood damage, risk distribution, and adaptive behavior. The emphasis is on understanding how these approaches have been operationalized in real-world settings.

4.1. Spatial sorting models

Sorting and spatial-equilibrium models have been widely used to analyse how households and firms choose locations given differences in preferences, amenities, and risks. Their empirical strength lies in linking behavioural theory to observed market outcomes - particularly housing prices, wages, and demographic patterns - to infer preferences and welfare effects. Internationally, sorting models have been applied to a broad range of topics (e.g., Melstrom et al., 2021; Bayer et al., 2016). Notable examples of application are Kuminoff et al. (2013) and Klaiber and Phaneuf (2010), who both recover household preferences for environmental quality and risk in order to evaluate land-use policies.

In the Danish context, spatial-equilibrium sorting models have, to our knowledge, been applied only once. Mulalic and Rouwendal (2020) use spatial sorting models to analyse how access to high-quality public transport - specifically the Copenhagen metro network - influences household car ownership, showing that public transport can act as a significant substitute for private vehicles in urban areas. In the context of flooding, the approach has been used also once: Bakkensen and Ma (2020) find that low-income and minority households are more likely to sort into high-risk flood zones, but also that re-sorting following policy reforms leads to fewer individuals residing in these areas. The limited number of sorting-model applications in Denmark and on flood-related topics more broadly likely reflects the demanding theoretical and empirical requirements needed to estimate spatial equilibrium models. However, sorting models provide a promising framework for analyzing how socio-economic development shapes exposure and vulnerability through location decisions.

4.2. Agent-based models

Agent-based models have seen limited use in Denmark, but existing applications demonstrate the feasibility of modelling heterogeneous behavior and market dynamics. The SMILE microsimulation model (Hansen et al., 2021) projects demographic and housing outcomes at the municipal level; although its spatial resolution is too coarse for flood exposure analysis, it illustrates how micro-level heterogeneity can be represented in national policy settings. Other Danish agent-based models focus on transport behavior (Ahanchian et al., 2019) and macroprudential housing regulation (Cokayne, 2019), confirming that Danish register data support behavioral simulation even if land-use dynamics in flood-prone areas have not yet been modelled.

Internationally, agent-based models have been more widely applied to land-use and housing market dynamics. Models such as RHEA (Filatova, 2015) and CHALMS (Magliocca et al., 2015) embed microeconomic foundations—including hedonic price functions, adaptive expectations, and optimizing behavior - into spatially explicit simulations of urban development. Other studies, such as those for Qazvin and Tehran (Hosseinali et al., 2013; Jokar Arsanjani et al., 2013), use empirically calibrated decision rules to predict urban expansion, while larger-scale applications such as CRAFTY-GB simulate land-use competition under climate and socio-economic scenarios (Brown et al., 2022).

Agent-based models have also been used to examine flood-related behavior and adaptation. Examples include models of housing market responses and insurance mechanisms in London (Dubbelboer et al., 2017), community flood risk and mitigation behavior in the United States (Tonn & Guikema, 2018), and climate-driven migration in France (Tierolf et al., 2023). A recent review highlights two main strands of flood-related agent-based models - those centered on hazard/vulnerability dynamics and those focused on markets and relocation

decisions—often drawing on expected utility theory and behavioral extensions such as Prospect Theory (Taberna et al., 2020). Collectively, this research shows that agent-based models can represent both economically motivated decisions and behavioral responses to changing flood risk, making them a relevant methodological alternative for modelling long-run exposure trajectories.

4.3. Predictive models

Predictive land-use change models - often based on statistical learning, cellular automata, or hybrid machine-learning frameworks -are widely used to project spatial development under alternative socio-economic and planning scenarios. In Denmark, several applications demonstrate the ability of predictive models to translate qualitative planning goals into quantitative land-use outcomes. Fertner et al. (2012) apply the Metronamica cellular automata model to assess the regional planning framework of the Fingerplan in Greater Copenhagen, and show that restrictive planning policies substantially limit urban expansion outside the designated “fingers.” Similarly, Fuglsang et al. (2013) use a land-use and land-cover cellular automata model to simulate three planning scenarios for Eastern Denmark, finding that more compact and coherent development patterns emerge under strategies prioritizing densification. These studies illustrate how predictive, spatially explicit cellular automata models can be used to explore alternative development paths when detailed behavioral modelling is not feasible.

Internationally, predictive modelling of land-use change increasingly relies on machine-learning and hybrid frameworks that combine cellular automata with statistical or learning algorithms. Shafizadeh-Moghadam et al. (2017) demonstrate that hybrid models outperform traditional logistic regression in predicting urban growth, with spatial coordinate, accessibility, and proximity variables emerging as dominant drivers. Comparative studies likewise show that hybrid cellular automata machine learning models provide high accuracy in simulating land-use transitions (Sankarrao et al., 2021), while reviews emphasize the strong performance of machine learning methods to predict complex socio-environmental change (Aburas et al., 2019; Chaturvedi & de Vries, 2021). These studies broadly conclude that machine-learning models capture spatial dependencies and nonlinearities more effectively than conventional land-use and land-change models based on classical statistics.

Predictive models have also been applied directly to assess how projected land-use change affects future flood risk. Barredo and Engelen (2010) integrate a cellular automata-based land-use model with flood hazard maps to estimate exposure under alternative development scenarios, finding that continued low-density expansion drives increasing flood exposure despite historical flood events. Recent studies further combine machine learning based land-use projections with vulnerability and hydraulic models to quantify changes in expected flood damages. For example, Gholami et al. (2024) show that land-use change—particularly urban expansion and deforestation—substantially increases flood vulnerability in northern Iran.

More broadly, systematic reviews conclude that cellular automata predictive models remain among the most frequently applied tools for predicting built-up expansion in flood-prone areas (Mardalena, 2024), with predictor variables typically including Land-use and land change, population growth, rainfall, slope, GDP, and distance to rivers, roads, and urban centers.

Together, this literature demonstrates that predictive and machine-learning models offer a flexible and empirically driven approach to projecting land-use change and associated exposure. Their primary limitation is that most models rely heavily on past land-use patterns and rarely incorporate socio-economic drivers explicitly, which may constrain their reliability to predict the future when structural conditions change.

5. Discussion and Recommendations

This working paper examined how societal development can be integrated into future flood damage assessments by clarifying the theoretical and methodological foundations for modelling dynamic exposure. Current Danish flood risk assessments generally assume static socio-economic and land-use conditions. Yet, demographic change, housing market dynamics, and spatial development patterns shape exposure and vulnerability over time. The central contribution of this paper is therefore conceptual: it identifies the gap between prevailing assessment practices and the socio-economic processes that govern long-run exposure, and it outlines how different modelling approaches could be adapted to address this limitation.

A key insight is that predictive, agent-based, and sorting models represent *competing modelling paradigms*, each built on distinct assumptions about behavior, information, and market adjustment. Predictive statistical and machine-learning models offer strong empirical performance when structural relationships are relatively stable, making them suitable for near-term projections of land-use change and exposure. Their main limitation is that they rely on extrapolation and do not model the mechanisms that produce structural change. As a result, they are vulnerable to non-stationarity - precisely the challenge posed by accelerating climate impacts, shifting risk perceptions, and evolving planning policies. For short-term operational purposes, these models remain valuable, but they are not designed to evaluate long-term adaptation strategies.

In contrast, structural approaches - sorting models and agent-based models - provide richer behavioral foundations that allow for counterfactual analysis and long-run scenario exploration. Sorting models derive spatial outcomes from equilibrium conditions based on utility or profit maximization and therefore enable welfare-consistent evaluation of major adaptation strategies. Their primary limitation is the strong informational and equilibrium assumptions required for estimation. Agent-based models, by contrast, relax these assumptions and allow heterogeneous agents to adapt gradually, learn, and respond to policy interventions under bounded rationality. They are well-suited to modelling transitions, social dynamics, and behavioral responses to flood risk, although they require extensive calibration and transparent behavioral specification. Taken together, these structural approaches offer alternatives to purely predictive modelling when the objective is to understand how behavioral change, policy design, and market responses shape long-run exposure.

The working paper also shows that Denmark is uniquely well-positioned to develop advanced socio-economic exposure models. Comprehensive administrative registers, detailed building inventories, geospatial hazard datasets, and municipal planning documents together provide the empirical foundation needed to represent household, firm, and land-use dynamics at high spatial resolution. These data assets make it feasible to estimate sorting models, initialize agent-based models with realistic heterogeneity, and train predictive models that capture detailed spatial trends. Nonetheless, specific gaps remain - most notably the limited availability of systematic historical loss data and incomplete documentation of adaptation measures. These gaps constrain the development and validation of vulnerability and damage functions and thus represent important priorities for future data integration.

A further implication of the paper is that all modelling approaches require scenario inputs. Climate projections, demographic and economic assumptions, land-use planning constraints, and adaptation strategies constitute exogenous elements that no model can generate internally. Scenario design, therefore, plays a critical role in determining the credibility and usefulness of any modelling exercise, regardless of whether the model is predictive, behavioral, or equilibrium-based. The choice of scenarios ultimately shapes the space of possible futures against which exposure and expected damages are evaluated.

In the paper, we suggest several important implications for Danish flood risk governance. National risk assessments could benefit from incorporating socio-economic dynamics to avoid misestimating long-term exposure. Integrating behavioral responses, demographic change, and land-use development into damage assessments would support more robust evaluations of coastal protection, land-use regulation, and long-term fiscal preparedness. Improved socio-economic modelling can also strengthen the alignment between spatial planning and climate adaptation, helping decision-makers anticipate where exposure is likely to grow and how policy interventions may shape future settlement patterns.

Future research should therefore focus on operationalizing the conceptual framework developed here. Promising directions include building a national land-use and socio-economic exposure model using register and geospatial data, perhaps by developing hybrid modelling strategies that combine predictive models with models that rely on structural insight, e.g., economic agent-based models or sorting models. Advancing these efforts would enhance Denmark's ability to develop coherent, forward-looking climate resilience strategies grounded in both physical and socio-economic realities.

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